

Kyasanur Forest Disease – A Re-emerging Tick-borne Viral Zoonoses

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Abstract

Zoonoses is a disease transmission occur from animals to humans and vice versa. When human infects the animals, it is called reverse zoonosis or anthroozoonosis. One of the re-emerging vectors borne zoonotic disease is Kyasanur Forest Disease (KFD), which is caused by Flavivirus characterized by Fever followed by Neurological complications. KFD was first reported in Kyasanur forest area, Shimoga district of Karnataka. It affects monkeys especially langur and humans. Humans are the dead-end host to this virus. The vector for transmission of KFDV is mainly through ticks especially the nymphs of *Haemaphysalis spinigera* and *Haemaphysalis turturis* species. The incubation period is 3-8 days. First stage is haemorrhagic fever and the second stage is meningoencephalitis. Kysanur forest disease can be diagnosed by PCR, ELISA and other molecular techniques. No specific treatment is available for Kyasanur Forest Disease. The target areas are the endemic areas in Karnataka, which should be periodically vaccinated.

Introduction

World zoonoses day is celebrated on 6th July every year. Zoonoses is a disease transmission occur from animals to humans. When human infects the animals, it is called reverse zoonosis or anthroozoonosis. The transmission of zoonotic disease occurs directly by aerosol, animal bites or indirectly by intermediate species (i.e., vector). The zoonotic disease ranges from mild infection to mortality. One of the re-emerging vectors borne zoonotic disease is Kyasanur Forest Disease (KFD)/ Haemorrhagic fever/monkey disease characterized by Fever followed by Neurological complications.

Etiology

The KFD virus is a member of the genus flavivirus and family Flaviviridae. The Flaviviridae is a family of positive, single-stranded, enveloped RNA virus. The KFD virus is immunologically similar to Alkhurma virus, Omsk hemorrhagic fever virus. The KFD virus measures about 25nm in diameter.

Hosts Interconnected

- The wild primates (Langurs, Macaques, Gibbons) and Humans are **the definitive host** for the KFD Virus.
- Rats, Shrews, Bats, Wild Avi-fauna acts as **Amplifier and reservoir Host** for this virus.
- Cattles and Buffaloes acts as **Maintenance host** for ticks *Haemaphysalis spinigera* .
- Panther, Dhole, Porcupine also acts as a **Maintenance host** for Ticks.
- Human is an **incidental or dead-end host**, there is no transmission between humans. Tribal forest-dwellers, Day labourers in plantations, Marginal farmers are highly prone to get the infection.

History

1957 – First reported in Kyasanur forest area, Shimoga district of Karnataka.

2012 - Reprted in Chikkamagalore, Uttara Kannada, Dakshina Kannada and Udupi districts and to Chamarajanagar district of Karnataka.

2013 – Reported in Necropsy of Monkeys in Nilgiris and also reported in Wayanad District of Kerala.

2014 – Reported in Malappuram district of Kerala.

2015 – Reported in Goa.

2016 - Reported in Sindhudurg district of Maharashtra.

Transmission

The vector for transmission of KFDV is mainly through ticks especially the nymphs of *Haemaphysalis spinigera* and *Haemaphysalis turturis* species. Man acquires the disease mainly during the dry season. To understand the transmission and the seasonal variation in disease incidence better, we must know about the life cycle of ticks.

1. Adults of tick species attach on large animals' mate and drop on ground. They lie dormant on forest floor and the female adults lays eggs in clusters. This occurs during rainy season.
2. The eggs hatch into larvae. They attach and feed on small and large mammals. The larvae get infected at this stage. The larvae fall on the ground after feeding and develop into nymphs. This occurs during dry season.
3. The nymphs can bite small mammals, Birds, Man, thus infecting them with KFDV. Monkeys and small mammals are the common host of KFDV. Man is the dead end of cycle of transmission. Man gets infected either by direct bite of infected tick or by contact with infected animal. No human-human transmission is reported.
4. The transmission peaks in the month of Jan-march where in the nymphs are abundant in number.
5. It is said that some nymphs may persist through the next season and be a reason for a new cycle of infection.
6. The adult ticks and larval feeding on the infected small mammals and large mammals can themselves get infected with the virus, passing it on to the nymphs, thus the cycle of infection continues.

Pathogenesis

Host Immune Response to The Virus

- The KFDV after entering into the body, targets the Antigen presenting cells (APC's) i.e. the dendritic cells and macrophages. Initial viral replication occurs in these cells, resulting in increased viral load and systemic spread of virus to organs like liver, spleen and other sites, thus producing the clinically manifested symptoms.
- The APC's present the viral antigen to T cells and produce Interferon-1 (IFN-1). IFN-1
- activates JAK-STAT signaling pathway leading to viral clearance. T-cells also produce
- IFN-1, in addition to activating B-cells to produce antibodies to neutralize the virus. It is
- noted that viral clearance is coinciding with peak of CD-8 T cell activation and IgG in blood.
- The APC's also produce cytokines for destroying the target cells.

Viral Response to Host Immune System

- KFDV produces NS-5 non-structural protein which inhibits the JAK-STAT pathway by antagonizing the interferon response.
- This leads to poor immune response and uncontrolled viral replication. The cytokine storm, poor immune response and increased viral load produces hematological and neurological complications.
- It also affects the coagulation pathway causing DIC (Disseminated Intravascular Coagulation) leading to death.

Clinical Features

The incubation period is 3-8 days. The disease usually has a biphasic presentation. First stage is haemorrhagic fever and the second stage is meningoencephalitis.

➤ First Stage

This stage is characterised by **sudden onset fever, frontal headache, myalgia, dehydration**. Ocular manifestations like serous discharge, conjunctival congestion is also seen. On examination **lymphadenopathy** and **hepato - splenomegaly** are seen. About 20% of patients move to second stage.

➤ Second Stage

This stage manifests as **drowsiness, transient disorientation, confusion, convulsions**. The case fatality rate is 2 - 10% . Higher fatality is noted in non-endemic areas due to lack of awareness and lower herd immunity to the virus.

Diagnosis

- Kysanur forest disease can be diagnosed by PCR, ELISA and other molecular techniques.
- By examining carcass lesions grossly and histopathological in necropsy of animals and autopsy of humans, we can diagnose KFD.
- Detecting tick prevalence in epidemic area.
- Blood collection in affected ones to view virus in viraemic stage.

Treatment

No specific treatment is available for Kysanur Forest Disease. Only conservative management of symptoms with NSAIDs for fever, rehydration by Fluid Therapy, management of Low platelet count etc. are carried out.

Prevention and Control

1. Vaccination

Formalin inactivated chick embryo vaccine is used. The target areas are the endemic areas in Karnataka. The schedule is 2 doses at 2-month interval followed by a booster at 6-9 months and then every 5 years once.

2. Avoid direct contact with Wild animals and Birds.

3. Tick Control

Vector control may be done by dusting with Malathion or by spraying. Repellents may be used on body/exposed parts during venture into forests.

4. Personal Safety

Pathologists and Forensic Medicine Experts are advised to take pre-cautionary measures before undergoing a Necropsy/Autopsy suspected for KFD.

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